

It is also important not to misconstrue these data as an attack on China or a suggestion that Chinese investment in Australian research should diminish, or grow. Rather, it is an observation about the international nature of funding of research projects at Australian universities.

Associate Professor Lucy Montgomery, COKI project co-lead, Curtin University

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